

Geometry on Non-Solvable Equations

– *A Review on Contradictory Systems*

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Abstract: As we known, an objective thing not moves with one's volition, which implies that all contradictions, particularly, in these semiotic systems for things are artificial. In classical view, a contradictory system is meaningless, contrast to that of geometry on figures of things caught by eyes of human beings. The main objective of sciences is holding the global behavior of things, which needs one knowing both of compatible and contradictory systems on things. Usually, a mathematical system including contradictions is said to be a *Smarandache system*. Beginning from a famous fable, i.e., the 6 blind men with an elephant, this report shows the geometry on contradictory systems, including non-solvable algebraic linear or homogenous equations, non-solvable ordinary differential equations and non-solvable partial differential equations, classify such systems and characterize their global behaviors by combinatorial geometry, particularly, the global stability of non-solvable differential equations. Applications of such systems to other sciences, such as those of gravitational fields, ecologically industrial systems can be also found in this report. All of these discussions show that a non-solvable system is nothing else but a system underlying a topological graph $G \not\cong K_n$, or $\simeq K_n$ without common intersection, contrast to those of solvable systems underlying K_n being with common non-empty intersections, where n is the number of equations in this system. However, if we stand on a geometrical viewpoint, they are compatible and both of them are meaningful for human beings.

Key Words: Smarandache system, non-solvable system of equations, topological graph, G^L -solution, global stability, ecologically industrial systems, gravitational field, mathematical combinatorics.

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§1. Introduction

A *contradiction* is a difference between two statements, beliefs, or ideas about something that can not both be true, exists everywhere and usually with a presentation as argument, debate, disputing, \dots , etc., even break out a war sometimes. Among them, a widely known contradiction in philosophy happened in a famous fable, i.e., the 6 blind men with an elephant following.

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Fig.1

In this fable, there are 6 blind men were asked to determine what an elephant looked like by feeling different parts of the elephant's body. The man touched the elephant's leg, tail, trunk, ear, belly or tusk respectively claims it's like a pillar, a rope, a tree branch, a hand fan, a wall or a solid pipe, such as those shown in Fig.1. Each of them insisted on his own and not accepted others. They then entered into an endless argument. *All of you are right!* A wise man explains to them: *why are you telling it differently is because each one of you touched the different part of the elephant. So, actually the elephant has all those features what you all said.* Thus, the best result on an elephant for these blind men is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{An elephant} = & \{4 \text{ pillars}\} \cup \{1 \text{ rope}\} \cup \{1 \text{ tree branch}\} \\ & \cup \{2 \text{ hand fans}\} \cup \{1 \text{ wall}\} \cup \{1 \text{ solid pipe}\}, \end{aligned}$$

i.e., a *Smarandache multi-space* ([23]-[25]) defined following.

Definition 1.1([12]-[13]) *Let $(\Sigma_1; \mathcal{R}_1), (\Sigma_2; \mathcal{R}_2), \dots, (\Sigma_m; \mathcal{R}_m)$ be m mathematical systems, different two by two. A Smarandache multi-system $\tilde{\Sigma}$ is a union $\bigcup_{i=1}^m \Sigma_i$ with rules $\tilde{\mathcal{R}} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m \mathcal{R}_i$ on $\tilde{\Sigma}$, denoted by $(\tilde{\Sigma}; \tilde{\mathcal{R}})$.*

Then, what is the philosophical meaning of this fable for one understanding the world? In fact, the situation for one realizing behaviors of things is analogous to the blind men determining what an elephant looks like. Thus, this fable means the limitation or unilateral of one's knowledge, i.e., *science* because of all of those are just correspondent with the sensory cognition of human beings.

Besides, we know that contradiction exists everywhere by this fable, which comes from the limitation of unilateral sensory cognition, i.e., artificial contradiction of human beings, and all scientific conclusions are nothing else but an approximation for things. For example, let $\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_n$ be known and $\nu_i, i \geq 1$ unknown characters at time t for a thing T . Then, the

thing T should be understood by

$$T = \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n \{\mu_i\} \right) \cup \left(\bigcup_{k \geq 1} \{\nu_k\} \right)$$

in logic but with an approximation $T^\circ = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \{\mu_i\}$ for T by human being at time t . Even for T° , these are maybe contradictions in characters $\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_n$ with endless argument between researchers, such as those implied in the fable of 6 blind men with an elephant. Consequently, if one stands still on systems without contradictions, he will never hold the real face of things in the world, particularly, the true essence of geometry for limited of his time.

However, all things are inherently related, not isolated in philosophy, i.e., underlying an invariant topological structure G ([4],[22]). Thus, one needs to characterize those things on contradictory systems, particularly, by geometry. The main objective of this report is to discuss the geometry on contradictory systems, including non-solvable algebraic equations, non-solvable ordinary or partial differential equations, classify such systems and characterize their global behaviors by combinatorial geometry, particularly, the global stability of non-solvable differential equations. For terminologies and notations not mentioned here, we follow references [11], [13] for topological graphs, [3]-[4] for topology, [12],[23]-[25] for Smarandache multi-spaces and [2],[26] for partial or ordinary differential equations.

§2. Geometry on Non-Solvable Equations

Loosely speaking, a geometry is mainly concerned with shape, size, position, \dots etc., i.e., local or global characters of a figure in space. Its mainly objective is to hold the global behavior of things. However, things are always complex, even hybrid with other things. So it is difficult to know its global characters, or true face of a thing sometimes.

Let us beginning with two systems of linear equations in 2 variables:

$$(LES_4^S) \begin{cases} x + 2y = 4 \\ 2x + y = 5 \\ x - 2y = 0 \\ 2x - y = 3 \end{cases} \quad (LES_4^N) \begin{cases} x + 2y = 2 \\ x + 2y = -2 \\ 2x - y = -2 \\ 2x - y = 2 \end{cases}$$

Clearly, (LES_4^S) is solvable with a solution $x = 2$ and $y = 1$, but (LES_4^N) is not because $x + 2y = -2$ is contradictious to $x + 2y = 2$, and so that for equations $2x - y = -2$ and $2x - y = 2$. Thus, (LES_4^N) is a contradiction system, i.e., a Smarandache system defined following.

Definition 2.1([11]-[13]) *A rule in a mathematical system $(\Sigma; \mathcal{R})$ is said to be Smarandachely denied if it behaves in at least two different ways within the same set Σ , i.e., validated and invalidated, or only invalidated but in multiple distinct ways.*

A Smarandache system $(\Sigma; \mathcal{R})$ is a mathematical system which has at least one Smarandachely denied rule in \mathcal{R} .

In geometry, we are easily finding conditions for systems of equations solvable or not. For integers $m, n \geq 1$, denote by

$$S_{f_i} = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) | f_i(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) = 0\} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$$

the solution-manifold in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} for integers $1 \leq i \leq m$, where f_i is a function hold with conditions of the implicit function theorem for $1 \leq i \leq m$. Clearly, the system

$$(ES_m) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} f_1(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) = 0 \\ \dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots \\ f_m(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) = 0 \end{array} \right.$$

is solvable or not dependent on

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^m S_{f_i} \neq \emptyset \text{ or } = \emptyset.$$

Conversely, if \mathcal{D} is a geometrical space consisting of m manifolds $\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2, \dots, \mathcal{D}_m$ in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} , where,

$$\mathcal{D}_i = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) | f_k^{[i]}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) = 0, 1 \leq k \leq m_i\} = \bigcap_{k=1}^{m_i} S_{f_k^{[i]}}.$$

Then, the system

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} f_1^{[i]}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) = 0 \\ \dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots \\ f_{m_i}^{[i]}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) = 0 \end{array} \right\} 1 \leq i \leq m$$

is solvable or not dependent on the intersection

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^m \mathcal{D}_i \neq \emptyset \text{ or } = \emptyset.$$

Thus, we obtain the following result.

Theorem 2.2 *If a geometrical space \mathcal{D} consists of m parts $\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2, \dots, \mathcal{D}_m$, where, $\mathcal{D}_i = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) | f_k^{[i]}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) = 0, 1 \leq k \leq m_i\}$, then the system (ES_m) consisting of*

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} f_1^{[i]}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) = 0 \\ \dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots\dots \\ f_{m_i}^{[i]}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) = 0 \end{array} \right\} 1 \leq i \leq m$$

is non-solvable if $\bigcap_{i=1}^m \mathcal{D}_i = \emptyset$.

Now, *whether is it meaningless for a contradiction system in the world?* Certainly not! As we discussed in the last section, a contradiction is artificial if such a system indeed exists in the world. The objective for human beings is not just finding contradictions, but holds behaviors of such systems. For example, although the system (LES_4^N) is contradictory, but it really exists, i.e., 4 lines in \mathbb{R}^2 , such as those shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2

Generally, let

$$AX = (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m)^T \quad (LEq)$$

be a linear equation system with

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \cdots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad X = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \cdots \\ x_n \end{bmatrix}$$

for integers $m, n \geq 1$. A vertex-edge labeled graph $G^L[LEq]$ on such a system is defined by:

$V(G^L[LEq]) = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_m\}$, where $P_i = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) | a_{i1}x_1 + a_{i2}x_2 + \dots + a_{in}x_n = b_i\}$, $E(G^L[LEq]) = \{(P_i, P_j), P_i \cap P_j \neq \emptyset, 1 \leq i, j \leq m\}$ and labeled with $L : P_i \rightarrow P_i$, $L : (P_i, P_j) \rightarrow P_i \cap P_j$ for integers $1 \leq i, j \leq m$ with an underlying graph $\widehat{G}[LEq]$ without labels.

For example, let $L_1 = \{(x, y) | x + 2y = 2\}$, $L_2 = \{(x, y) | x + 2y = -2\}$, $L_3 = \{(x, y) | 2x - y = 2\}$ and $L_4 = \{(x, y) | 2x - y = -2\}$ for the system (LES_4^N) . Clearly, $L_1 \cap L_2 = \emptyset$, $L_1 \cap L_3 = \{B\}$, $L_1 \cap L_4 = \{A\}$, $L_2 \cap L_3 = \{C\}$, $L_2 \cap L_4 = \{D\}$ and $L_3 \cap L_4 = \emptyset$. Then, the system (LES_4^N) can also appears as a vertex-edge labeled graph C_4^l in \mathbb{R}^2 with labels vertex labeling

$l(L_i) = L_i$ for integers $1 \leq i \leq 4$, edge labeling $l(L_1, L_3) = B$, $l(L_1, L_4) = A$, $l(L_2, L_3) = C$ and $l(L_2, L_4) = D$, such as those shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3

We are easily to determine $\widehat{G}[LEq]$ for systems (LEq) . For integers $1 \leq i, j \leq m$, $i \neq j$, two linear equations

$$\begin{aligned} a_{i1}x_1 + a_{i2}x_2 + \cdots + a_{in}x_n &= b_i, \\ a_{j1}x_1 + a_{j2}x_2 + \cdots + a_{jn}x_n &= b_j \end{aligned}$$

are called *parallel* if there exists a constant c such that

$$c = a_{j1}/a_{i1} = a_{j2}/a_{i2} = \cdots = a_{jn}/a_{in} \neq b_j/b_i.$$

Otherwise, *non-parallel*. The following result is known in [16].

Theorem 2.3([16]) *Let (LEq) be a linear equation system for integers $m, n \geq 1$. Then $\widehat{G}[LEq] \simeq K_{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_s}$ with $n_1 + n_2 + \cdots + n_s = m$, where \mathcal{C}_i is the parallel family by the property that all equations in a family \mathcal{C}_i are parallel and there are no other equations parallel to lines in \mathcal{C}_i for integers $1 \leq i \leq s$, $n_i = |\mathcal{C}_i|$ for integers $1 \leq i \leq s$ in (LEq) and (LEq) is non-solvable if $s \geq 2$.*

Particularly, for linear equation system on 2 variables, let H be a planar graph with edges straight segments on \mathbb{R}^2 . The *c-line graph* $L_C(H)$ on H is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} V(L_C(H)) &= \{\text{straight lines } L = e_1 e_2 \cdots e_l, s \geq 1 \text{ in } H\}; \\ E(L_C(H)) &= \{(L_1, L_2) \mid L_1 = e_1^1 e_2^1 \cdots e_l^1, L_2 = e_1^2 e_2^2 \cdots e_s^2, l, s \geq 1 \\ &\quad \text{and there adjacent edges } e_i^1, e_j^2 \text{ in } H, 1 \leq i \leq l, 1 \leq j \leq s\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, a simple criterion in [16] following is interesting.

Theorem 2.4([16]) *A linear equation system $(LEq2)$ on 2 variables is non-solvable if and only if $\widehat{G}[LEq2] \simeq L_C(H)$, where H is a planar graph of order $|H| \geq 2$ on \mathbb{R}^2 with each edge a straight segment*

Generally, a Smarandache multi-system is equivalent to a combinatorial system by following, which implies the *CC Conjecture* for mathematics, i.e., *any mathematics can be recon-*

structed from or turned into combinatorization (see [6] for details).

Definition 2.5([11]-[13]) For any integer $m \geq 1$, let $(\tilde{\Sigma}; \tilde{\mathcal{R}})$ be a Smarandache multi-system consisting of m mathematical systems $(\Sigma_1; \mathcal{R}_1), (\Sigma_2; \mathcal{R}_2), \dots, (\Sigma_m; \mathcal{R}_m)$. An inherited topological structure $G^L[\tilde{S}]$ of $(\tilde{\Sigma}; \tilde{\mathcal{R}})$ is a topological vertex-edge labeled graph defined following:

$$\begin{aligned} V(G^L[\tilde{S}]) &= \{\Sigma_1, \Sigma_2, \dots, \Sigma_m\}, \\ E(G^L[\tilde{S}]) &= \{(\Sigma_i, \Sigma_j) \mid \Sigma_i \cap \Sigma_j \neq \emptyset, 1 \leq i \neq j \leq m\} \text{ with labeling} \\ L: \Sigma_i &\rightarrow L(\Sigma_i) = \Sigma_i \quad \text{and} \quad L: (\Sigma_i, \Sigma_j) \rightarrow L(\Sigma_i, \Sigma_j) = \Sigma_i \cap \Sigma_j \end{aligned}$$

for integers $1 \leq i \neq j \leq m$.

Therefore, a Smarandache system is equivalent to a combinatorial system, i.e., $(\tilde{\Sigma}; \tilde{\mathcal{R}}) \simeq G^L[\tilde{S}]$, a labeled graph $\widehat{G}^L[\tilde{S}]$ by this notion. For examples, denoting by $a = \{\text{tusk}\} b = \{\text{nose}\} c_1, c_2 = \{\text{ear}\} d = \{\text{head}\} e = \{\text{neck}\} f = \{\text{trunk}\} g_1, g_2, g_3, g_4 = \{\text{leg}\} h = \{\text{tail}\}$ for an elephant then a topological structure for an elephant is shown in Fig.4 following.

Fig.4 Topological structure of an elephant

For geometry, let these mathematical systems $(\Sigma_1; \mathcal{R}_1), (\Sigma_2; \mathcal{R}_2), \dots, (\Sigma_m; \mathcal{R}_m)$ be geometrical spaces, for instance manifolds M_1, M_2, \dots, M_m with respective dimensions n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m in Definition 2.3, we get a geometrical space $\widetilde{M} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m M_i$ underlying a topological graph $G^L[\widetilde{M}]$. Such a geometrical space $G^L[\widetilde{M}]$ is said to be *combinatorial manifold*, denoted by $\widetilde{M}(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)$. Particularly, if $n_i = n, 1 \leq i \leq m$, then a combinatorial manifold $\widetilde{M}(n_1, \dots, n_m)$ is nothing else but an n -manifold underlying $G^L[\widetilde{M}]$. However, this presentation of G^L -systems contributes to manifolds and combinatorial manifolds (See [7]-[15] for details). For example, the fundamental groups of manifolds are characterized in [14]-[15] following.

Theorem 2.6([14]) For any locally compact n -manifold M , there always exists an inherent graph $G_{min}^{in}[M]$ of M such that $\pi(M) \cong \pi(G_{min}^{in}[M])$.

Particularly, for an integer $n \geq 2$ a compact n -manifold M is simply-connected if and only if $G_{min}^{in}[M]$ is a finite tree.

Theorem 2.7([15]) Let \widetilde{M} be a finitely combinatorial manifold. If for $\forall(M_1, M_2) \in E(G^L[\widetilde{M}])$,

$M_1 \cap M_2$ is simply-connected, then

$$\pi_1(\widetilde{M}) \cong \left(\bigoplus_{M \in V(G[\widetilde{M}])} \pi_1(M) \right) \bigoplus \pi_1(G[\widetilde{M}]).$$

Furthermore, it provides one with a listing of manifolds by graphs in [14].

Theorem 2.8([14]) *Let $\mathcal{A}[M] = \{ (U_\lambda; \varphi_\lambda) \mid \lambda \in \Lambda \}$ be a atlas of a locally compact n -manifold M . Then the labeled graph $G_{|\Lambda|}^L$ of M is a topological invariant on $|\Lambda|$, i.e., if $H_{|\Lambda|}^{L_1}$ and $G_{|\Lambda|}^{L_2}$ are two labeled n -dimensional graphs of M , then there exists a self-homeomorphism $h : M \rightarrow M$ such that $h : H_{|\Lambda|}^{L_1} \rightarrow G_{|\Lambda|}^{L_2}$ naturally induces an isomorphism of graph.*

For a combinatorial surface consisting of surfaces associated with homogenous polynomials in \mathbb{R}^3 , we can further determine its genus. Let

$$P_1(\bar{x}), P_2(\bar{x}), \dots, P_m(\bar{x}) \quad (ES_m^{n+1})$$

be m homogeneous polynomials in variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1} with coefficients in \mathbb{C} and

$$\emptyset \neq S_{P_i} = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n+1}) \mid P_i(\bar{x}) = 0\} \subset \mathbb{P}^n \mathbb{C}$$

for integers $1 \leq i \leq m$, which are hypersurfaces, particularly, curves if $n = 2$ passing through the original of \mathbb{C}^{n+1} .

Similarly, parallel hypersurfaces in \mathbb{C}^{n+1} are defined following.

Definition 2.9 *Let $P(\bar{x}), Q(\bar{x})$ be two complex homogenous polynomials of degree d in $n + 1$ variables and $I(P, Q)$ the set of intersection points of $P(\bar{x})$ with $Q(\bar{x})$. They are said to be parallel, denoted by $P \parallel Q$ if $d > 1$ and there are constants a, b, \dots, c (not all zero) such that for $\forall \bar{x} \in I(P, Q)$, $ax_1 + bx_2 + \dots + cx_{n+1} = 0$, i.e., all intersections of $P(\bar{x})$ with $Q(\bar{x})$ appear at a hyperplane on $\mathbb{P}^n \mathbb{C}$, or $d = 1$ with all intersections at the infinite $x_{n+1} = 0$. Otherwise, $P(\bar{x})$ are not parallel to $Q(\bar{x})$, denoted by $P \not\parallel Q$.*

Then, these polynomials in (ES_m^{n+1}) can be classified into families $\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \dots, \mathcal{C}_l$ by this parallel property such that $P_i \parallel P_j$ if $P_i, P_j \in \mathcal{C}_k$ for an integer $1 \leq k \leq l$, where $1 \leq i \neq j \leq m$ and it is *maximal* if each \mathcal{C}_i is maximal for integers $1 \leq i \leq l$, i.e., for $\forall P \in \{P_k(\bar{x}), 1 \leq k \leq m\} \setminus \mathcal{C}_i$, there is a polynomial $Q(\bar{x}) \in \mathcal{C}_i$ such that $P \not\parallel Q$. The following result is a generalization of Theorem 2.3.

Theorem 2.10([19]) *Let $n \geq 2$ be an integer. For a system (ES_m^{n+1}) of homogenous polynomials with a parallel maximal classification $\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \dots, \mathcal{C}_l$,*

$$\widehat{G}[ES_m^{n+1}] \leq K(\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \dots, \mathcal{C}_l)$$

and with equality holds if and only if $P_i \parallel P_j$ and $P_s \not\parallel P_i$ implies that $P_s \not\parallel P_j$, where

$K(\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \dots, \mathcal{C}_l)$ denotes a complete l -partite graphs. Conversely, for any subgraph $G \leq K(\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \dots, \mathcal{C}_l)$, there are systems (ES_m^{n+1}) of homogenous polynomials with a parallel maximal classification $\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \dots, \mathcal{C}_l$ such that

$$G \simeq \widehat{G}[ES_m^{n+1}].$$

Particularly, if all polynomials in (ES_m^{n+1}) be degree 1, i.e., hyperplanes with a parallel maximal classification $\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \dots, \mathcal{C}_l$, then

$$\widehat{G}[ES_m^{n+1}] = K(\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \dots, \mathcal{C}_l).$$

The following result is immediately known by definition.

Theorem 2.11 Let (ES_m^{n+1}) be a G^L -system consisting of homogenous polynomials $P(\bar{x}_1), P(\bar{x}_2), \dots, P(\bar{x}_m)$ in $n+1$ variables with respectively hypersurfaces $S_{P_i}, 1 \leq i \leq m$. Then, $\widetilde{M} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m S_{P_i}$ is an n -manifold underlying graph $\widehat{G}[ES_m^{n+1}]$ in \mathbb{C}^{n+1} .

For $n = 2$, we can further determine the genus of surface \widetilde{M} in \mathbb{R}^3 following.

Theorem 2.12([19]) Let \widetilde{S} be a combinatorial surface consisting of m orientable surfaces S_1, S_2, \dots, S_m underlying a topological graph $G^L[\widetilde{S}]$ in \mathbb{R}^3 . Then

$$g(\widetilde{S}) = \beta(\widehat{G}\langle\widetilde{S}\rangle) + \sum_{i=1}^m (-1)^{i+1} \sum_{\bigcap_{l=1}^i S_{k_l} \neq \emptyset} \left[g\left(\bigcap_{l=1}^i S_{k_l}\right) - c\left(\bigcap_{l=1}^i S_{k_l}\right) + 1 \right],$$

where $g\left(\bigcap_{l=1}^i S_{k_l}\right)$, $c\left(\bigcap_{l=1}^i S_{k_l}\right)$ are respectively the genus and number of path-connected components in surface $S_{k_1} \cap S_{k_2} \cap \dots \cap S_{k_i}$ and $\beta(\widehat{G}\langle\widetilde{S}\rangle)$ denotes the Betti number of topological graph $\widehat{G}\langle\widetilde{S}\rangle$.

Notice that for a curve C determined by homogenous polynomial $P(x, y, z)$ of degree d in $\mathbb{P}^2\mathbf{C}$, there is a compact connected Riemann surface S by the Noether's result such that

$$h : S - h^{-1}(\text{Sing}(C)) \rightarrow C - \text{Sing}(C)$$

is a homeomorphism with genus

$$g(S) = \frac{1}{2}(d-1)(d-2) - \sum_{p \in \text{Sing}(C)} \delta(p),$$

where $\delta(p)$ is a positive integer associated with the singular point p in C . Furthermore, if $\text{Sing}(C) = \emptyset$, i.e., C is non-singular then there is a compact connected Riemann surface S homeomorphism to C with genus $\frac{1}{2}(d-1)(d-2)$. By Theorem 2.12, we obtain the genus of \widetilde{S}

determined by homogenous polynomials following.

Theorem 2.13([19]) *Let C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m be complex curves determined by homogenous polynomials $P_1(x, y, z), P_2(x, y, z), \dots, P_m(x, y, z)$ without common component, and let*

$$R_{P_i, P_j} = \prod_{k=1}^{\deg(P_i)\deg(P_j)} (c_k^{ij}z - b_k^{ij}y)^{e_k^{ij}}, \quad \omega_{i,j} = \sum_{k=1}^{\deg(P_i)\deg(P_j)} \sum_{e_k^{ij} \neq 0} 1$$

be the resultant of $P_i(x, y, z), P_j(x, y, z)$ for $1 \leq i \neq j \leq m$. Then there is an orientable surface \tilde{S} in \mathbb{R}^3 of genus

$$\begin{aligned} g(\tilde{S}) &= \beta(\widehat{G} \langle \tilde{C} \rangle) + \sum_{i=1}^m \left(\frac{(\deg(P_i) - 1)(\deg(P_i) - 2)}{2} - \sum_{p^i \in \text{Sing}(C_i)} \delta(p^i) \right) \\ &+ \sum_{1 \leq i \neq j \leq m} (\omega_{i,j} - 1) + \sum_{i \geq 3} (-1)^i \sum_{C_{k_1} \cap \dots \cap C_{k_i} \neq \emptyset} \left[c(C_{k_1} \cap \dots \cap C_{k_i}) - 1 \right] \end{aligned}$$

with a homeomorphism $\varphi : \tilde{S} \rightarrow \tilde{C} = \bigcup_{i=1}^m C_i$. Furthermore, if C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m are non-singular, then

$$\begin{aligned} g(\tilde{S}) &= \beta(\widehat{G} \langle \tilde{C} \rangle) + \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{(\deg(P_i) - 1)(\deg(P_i) - 2)}{2} \\ &+ \sum_{1 \leq i \neq j \leq m} (\omega_{i,j} - 1) + \sum_{i \geq 3} (-1)^i \sum_{C_{k_1} \cap \dots \cap C_{k_i} \neq \emptyset} \left[c(C_{k_1} \cap \dots \cap C_{k_i}) - 1 \right], \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\delta(p^i) = \frac{1}{2} \left(I_{p^i} \left(P_i, \frac{\partial P_i}{\partial y} \right) - \nu_\phi(p^i) + |\pi^{-1}(p^i)| \right)$$

is a positive integer with a ramification index $\nu_\phi(p^i)$ for $p^i \in \text{Sing}(C_i), 1 \leq i \leq m$.

Notice that $\widehat{G} [ES_m^3] = K_m$. We then easily get conclusions following.

Corollary 2.14 *Let C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m be complex non-singular curves determined by homogenous polynomials $P_1(x, y, z), P_2(x, y, z), \dots, P_m(x, y, z)$ without common component, any intersection point $p \in I(P_i, P_j)$ with multiplicity 1 and*

$$\begin{cases} P_i(x, y, z) = 0 \\ P_j(x, y, z) = 0, \quad \forall i, j, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\} \\ P_k(x, y, z) = 0 \end{cases}$$

has zero-solution only. Then the genus of normalization \tilde{S} of curves C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m is

$$g(\tilde{S}) = 1 + \frac{1}{2} \times \sum_{i=1}^m \deg(P_i) (\deg(P_i) - 3) + \sum_{1 \leq i \neq j \leq m} \deg(P_i) \deg(P_j).$$

partial differential equations with initial values $u|_{x_n=x_n^0} = u_0$ is non-solvable if and only if the system $(LPDES_m)$ of partial differential equations is algebraically contradictory. Particularly, the Cauchy problem on a quasilinear partial differential equation is always solvable.

Similarly, for integers $m, n \geq 1$, let

$$\dot{X} = A_1 X, \dots, \dot{X} = A_k X, \dots, \dot{X} = A_m X \quad (LDES_m^1)$$

be a linear ordinary differential equation system of first order and

$$\begin{cases} x^{(n)} + a_{11}^{[0]} x^{(n-1)} + \dots + a_{1n}^{[0]} x = 0 \\ x^{(n)} + a_{21}^{[0]} x^{(n-1)} + \dots + a_{2n}^{[0]} x = 0 \\ \dots\dots\dots \\ x^{(n)} + a_{m1}^{[0]} x^{(n-1)} + \dots + a_{mn}^{[0]} x = 0 \end{cases} \quad (LDE_m^n)$$

a linear differential equation system of order n with

$$A_k = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11}^{[k]} & a_{12}^{[k]} & \dots & a_{1n}^{[k]} \\ a_{21}^{[k]} & a_{22}^{[k]} & \dots & a_{2n}^{[k]} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{n1}^{[k]} & a_{n2}^{[k]} & \dots & a_{nn}^{[k]} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad X = \begin{bmatrix} x_1(t) \\ x_2(t) \\ \dots \\ x_n(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

where each $a_{ij}^{[k]}$ is a real number for integers $0 \leq k \leq m, 1 \leq i, j \leq n$. Then it is known a criterion from [16] following.

Theorem 3.4([17]) *A differential equation system $(LDES_m^1)$ is non-solvable if and only if*

$$(|A_1 - \lambda I_{n \times n}|, |A_2 - \lambda I_{n \times n}|, \dots, |A_m - \lambda I_{n \times n}|) = 1.$$

Similarly, the differential equation system (LDE_m^n) is non-solvable if and only if

$$(P_1(\lambda), P_2(\lambda), \dots, P_m(\lambda)) = 1,$$

where $P_i(\lambda) = \lambda^n + a_{i1}^{[0]} \lambda^{n-1} + \dots + a_{i(n-1)}^{[0]} \lambda + a_{in}^{[0]}$ for integers $1 \leq i \leq m$. Particularly, $(LDES_m^1)$ and (LDE_m^n) are always solvable.

According to Theorems 3.3 and 3.4, for systems $(LPDES_m^C)$, $(LDES_m^1)$ or (LDE_m^n) , there are equivalent systems $G^L[LPDES_m^C]$, $G^L[LDES_m^1]$ or $G^L[LDE_m^n]$ by Definition 2.5, called $G^L[LPDES_m^C]$ -solution, $G^L[LDES_m^1]$ -solution or $G^L[LDE_m^n]$ -solution of systems $(LPDES_m^C)$, $(LDES_m^1)$ or (LDE_m^n) , respectively. Then, we know the following conclusion from [17]-[18], [21].

Theorem 3.5([17]-[18],[21]) *The Cauchy problem on system $(PDES_m)$ of partial differential equations of first order with initial values $x_i^{[k^0]}, u_0^{[k]}, p_i^{[k^0]}$, $1 \leq i \leq n$ for the k th equation in*

($PDES_m$), $1 \leq k \leq m$ such that

$$\frac{\partial u_0^{[k]}}{\partial s_j} - \sum_{i=0}^n p_i^{[k^0]} \frac{\partial x_i^{[k^0]}}{\partial s_j} = 0,$$

and the linear homogeneous differential equation system ($LDES_m^1$) (or (LDE_m^n)) both are uniquely G^L -solvable, i.e., $G^L[PDES]$, $G^L[LDES_m^1]$ and $G^L[LDE_m^n]$ are uniquely determined.

For ordinary differential systems ($LDES_m^1$) or (LDE_m^n), we can further replace solution-manifolds $S^{[k]}$ of the k th equation in $G^L[LDES_m^1]$ and $G^L[LDE_m^n]$ by their solution basis $\mathcal{B}^{[k]} = \{ \bar{\beta}_i^{[k]}(t)e^{\alpha_i^{[k]}t} \mid 1 \leq i \leq n \}$ or $\mathcal{C}^{[k]} = \{ t^l e^{\lambda_i^{[k]}t} \mid 1 \leq i \leq s, 1 \leq l \leq k_i \}$ because each solution-manifold of ($LDES_m^1$) (or (LDE_m^n)) is a linear space.

For example, let a system (LDE_m^n) be

$$\begin{cases} \ddot{x} - 3\dot{x} + 2x = 0 & (1) \\ \ddot{x} - 5\dot{x} + 6x = 0 & (2) \\ \ddot{x} - 7\dot{x} + 12x = 0 & (3) \\ \ddot{x} - 9\dot{x} + 20x = 0 & (4) \\ \ddot{x} - 11\dot{x} + 30x = 0 & (5) \\ \ddot{x} - 7\dot{x} + 6x = 0 & (6) \end{cases}$$

where $\ddot{x} = \frac{d^2x}{dt^2}$ and $\dot{x} = \frac{dx}{dt}$. Then the solution basis of equations (1) – (6) are respectively $\{e^t, e^{2t}\}$, $\{e^{2t}, e^{3t}\}$, $\{e^{3t}, e^{4t}\}$, $\{e^{4t}, e^{5t}\}$, $\{e^{5t}, e^{6t}\}$, $\{e^{6t}, e^t\}$ with its $G^L[LDE_m^n]$ shown in Fig.5.

Fig.5

Such a labeling can be simplified to labeling by integers for combinatorially classifying systems $G^L[LDES_m^1]$ and $G^L[LDE_m^n]$, i.e., *integral graphs* following.

Definition 3.6 Let G be a simple graph. A vertex-edge labeled graph $\theta : G \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^+$ is called *integral* if $\theta(uv) \leq \min\{\theta(u), \theta(v)\}$ for $\forall uv \in E(G)$, denoted by G^{I_θ} .

For two integral labeled graphs $G_1^{I_\theta}$ and $G_2^{I_\tau}$, they are called *identical* if $G_1 \stackrel{\varphi}{\cong} G_2$ and $\theta(x) = \tau(\varphi(x))$ for any graph isomorphism φ and $\forall x \in V(G_1) \cup E(G_1)$, denoted by $G_1^{I_\theta} = G_2^{I_\tau}$. Otherwise, *non-identical*.

For example, the graphs shown in Fig.6 are all integral on $K_4 - e$, but $G_1^{I_\theta} = G_2^{I_\tau}$, $G_1^{I_\theta} \neq G_3^{I_\sigma}$.

Fig.6

Applying integral graphs, the systems $(LDES_m^1)$ and (LDE_m^n) are combinatorially classified in [17] following.

Theorem 3.7([17]) *Let $(LDES_m^1)$, $(LDES_m^1)'$ (or (LDE_m^n) , $(LDE_m^n)'$) be two linear homogeneous differential equation systems with integral labeled graphs H, H' . Then $(LDES_m^1) \stackrel{\cong}{\simeq} (LDES_m^1)'$ (or $(LDE_m^n) \stackrel{\cong}{\simeq} (LDE_m^n)'$) if and only if $H = H'$.*

3.2 Differential Manifolds on G^L -Systems of Equations

By definition, the union $\widetilde{M} = \bigcup_{k=1}^m S^{[k]}$ is an n -manifold. The following result is immediately known.

Theorem 3.8([17]-[18],[21]) *For any simply graph G , there are differentiable solution-manifolds of $(PDES_m)$, $(LDES_m^1)$, (LDE_m^n) such that $\widehat{G}[PDES] \simeq G$, $\widehat{G}[LDES_m^1] \simeq G$ and $\widehat{G}[LDE_m^n] \simeq G$.*

Notice that a basis on vector field $T(M)$ of a differentiable n -manifold M is

$$\left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}, 1 \leq i \leq n \right\}$$

and a vector field X can be viewed as a first order partial differential operator

$$X = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i},$$

where a_i is C^∞ -differentiable for all integers $1 \leq i \leq n$. Combining Theorems 3.5 and 3.8 enables one to get a result on vector fields following.

Theorem 3.9([21]) *For an integer $m \geq 1$, let $U_i, 1 \leq i \leq m$ be open sets in \mathbb{R}^n underlying a graph defined by $V(G) = \{U_i | 1 \leq i \leq m\}$, $E(G) = \{(U_i, U_j) | U_i \cap U_j \neq \emptyset, 1 \leq i, j \leq m\}$. If X_i is a vector field on U_i for integers $1 \leq i \leq m$, then there always exists a differentiable manifold*

$M \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ with atlas $\mathcal{A} = \{(U_i, \phi_i) | 1 \leq i \leq m\}$ underlying graph G and a function $u_G \in \Omega^0(M)$ such that $X_i(u_G) = 0, 1 \leq i \leq m$.

§4. Applications

In philosophy, every thing is a G^L -system with contradictions embedded in our world, which implies that the geometry on non-solvable system of equations is in fact a truthful portraying of things with applications to various fields, particularly, the understanding on gravitational fields and the controlling of industrial systems.

4.1 Gravitational Fields

An immediate application of geometry on G^L -systems of non-solvable equations is that it can provides one with a visualization on things in space of dimension ≥ 4 by decomposing the space into subspaces underlying a graph G^L . For example, a decomposition of a Euclidean space into \mathbb{R}^3 is shown in Fig.7, where $G^L \simeq K_4$, a complete graph of order 4 and $\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \mathcal{P}_4$ are the observations on its subspaces \mathbb{R}^3 . This space model enable one to hold well local behaviors of the spacetime in \mathbb{R}^3 as usual and then determine its global behavior naturally, different from the *string theory* by artificial assuming the dimension of the universe is 11.

Fig.7

Notice that \mathbb{R}^3 is in a general position and maybe $\mathbb{R}^3 \cap \mathbb{R}^3 \neq \mathbb{R}^3$ here. Generally, if $G^L \simeq K_m$, we know its dimension following.

Theorem 4.1([9],[13]) *Let $\mathcal{E}_{K_m}(3)$ be a K_m -space of $\underbrace{\mathbb{R}_1^3, \dots, \mathbb{R}^3}_m$. Then its minimum dimension*

$$\dim_{min} \mathcal{E}_{K_m}(3) = \begin{cases} 3, & \text{if } m = 1, \\ 4, & \text{if } 2 \leq m \leq 4, \\ 5, & \text{if } 5 \leq m \leq 10, \\ 2 + \lceil \sqrt{m} \rceil, & \text{if } m \geq 11 \end{cases}$$

and maximum dimension

$$\dim_{\max} \mathcal{E}_{K_m}(3) = 2m - 1$$

with $\mathbb{R}_i^3 \cap \mathbb{R}_j^3 = \bigcap_{i=1}^m \mathbb{R}_i^3$ for any integers $1 \leq i, j \leq m$.

For the gravitational field, by applying the *geometrization of gravitation* in \mathbb{R}^3 , Einstein got his gravitational equations with time ([1])

$$R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg^{\mu\nu} + \lambda g^{\mu\nu} = -8\pi GT^{\mu\nu}$$

where $R^{\mu\nu} = R_{\alpha}^{\mu\alpha\nu} = g_{\alpha\beta}R^{\alpha\mu\beta\nu}$, $R = g_{\mu\nu}R^{\mu\nu}$ are the respective Ricci tensor, Ricci scalar curvature, $G = 6.673 \times 10^{-8} \text{cm}^3/\text{gs}^2$, $\kappa = 8\pi G/c^4 = 2.08 \times 10^{-48} \text{cm}^{-1} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^2$, which has a spherically symmetric solution on Riemannian metric, called *Schwarzschild spacetime*

$$ds^2 = f(t) \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right) dt^2 - \frac{1}{1 - \frac{r_s}{r}} dr^2 - r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2)$$

for $\lambda = 0$ in vacuum, where r_g is the *Schwarzschild radius*. Thus, if the dimension of the universe ≥ 4 , all these observations are nothing else but a projection of the true faces on our six organs, a pseudo-truth. However, we can characterize its global behavior by K_m^L -space solutions of \mathbb{R}^3 (See [8]-[10] for details). For example, if $m = 4$, there are 4 Einstein's gravitational equations for $\forall v \in V(K_4^L)$. We can solving it locally by spherically symmetric solutions in \mathbb{R}^3 and construct a K_4^L -solution $S_{f_1}, S_{f_2}, S_{f_3}$ and S_{f_4} , such as those shown in Fig.8,

Fig.8

where, each S_{f_i} is a geometrical space determined by Schwarzschild spacetime

$$ds^2 = f(t) \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right) dt^2 - \frac{1}{1 - \frac{r_s}{r}} dr^2 - r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2)$$

for integers $1 \leq i \leq m$. Certainly, its global behavior depends on the intersections $S_{f_i} \cap S_{f_j}$, $1 \leq i \neq j \leq 4$.

4.2 Ecologically Industrial Systems

Determining a system, particularly, an industrial system on initial values being stable or not is

an important problem because it reveals that this system is controllable or not by human beings. Usually, such a system is characterized by a system of differential equations. For example, let

$$\begin{cases} A \rightarrow X \\ 2X + Y \rightarrow 3X \\ B + X \rightarrow Y + D \\ X \rightarrow E \end{cases}$$

be the *Brusselator model* on chemical reaction, where A, B, X, Y are respectively the concentrations of 4 materials in this reaction. By the chemical dynamics if the initial concentrations for A, B are chosen sufficiently larger, then X and Y can be characterized by differential equations

$$\frac{\partial X}{\partial t} = k_1 \Delta X + A + X^2 Y - (B + 1)X, \quad \frac{\partial Y}{\partial t} = k_2 \Delta Y + BX - X^2 Y.$$

As we known, the stability of a system is determined by its solutions in classical sciences. But if the system of equations is non-solvable, *what is its stability?* It should be noted that non-solvable systems of equations extensively exist in our daily life. For example, an industrial system with raw materials M_1, M_2, \dots, M_n , products (including by-products) P_1, P_2, \dots, P_m but W_1, W_2, \dots, W_s wastes after a produce process, such as those shown in Fig.9 following,

Fig.9

which is an opened system and can be transferred to a closed one by letting the environment as an additional cell, called an *ecologically industrial system*. However, such an ecologically industrial system is usually a non-solvable system of equations by the input-output model in economy, see [20] for details.

Certainly, the global stability depends on the local stabilities. Applying the G -solution of a G^L -system (DES_m^C) of differential equations, the global stability is defined following.

Definition 4.2 Let $(PDES_m^C)$ be a Cauchy problem on a system of partial differential equations of first order in \mathbb{R}^n , $H \leq G[PDES_m^C]$ a spanning subgraph, and $u^{[v]}$ the solution of the v th

equation with initial value $u_0^{[v]}$, $v \in V(H)$. It is sum-stable on the subgraph H if for any number $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists, $\delta_v > 0$, $v \in V(H)$ such that each $G(t)$ -solution with

$$\left| u_0'^{[v]} - u_0^{[v]} \right| < \delta_v, \quad \forall v \in V(H)$$

exists for all $t \geq 0$ and with the inequality

$$\left| \sum_{v \in V(H)} u'^{[v]} - \sum_{v \in V(H)} u^{[v]} \right| < \varepsilon$$

holds, denoted by $G[t] \overset{H}{\sim} G[0]$ and $G[t] \overset{\Sigma}{\sim} G[0]$ if $H = G[PDES_m^C]$. Furthermore, if there exists a number $\beta_v > 0$, $v \in V(H)$ such that every $G'[t]$ -solution with

$$\left| u_0'^{[v]} - u_0^{[v]} \right| < \beta_v, \quad \forall v \in V(H)$$

satisfies

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left| \sum_{v \in V(H)} u'^{[v]} - \sum_{v \in V(H)} u^{[v]} \right| = 0,$$

then the $G[t]$ -solution is called asymptotically stable, denoted by $G[t] \overset{H}{\rightarrow} G[0]$ and $G[t] \overset{\Sigma}{\rightarrow} G[0]$ if $H = G[PDES_m^C]$.

Let $(PDES_m^C)$ be a system

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} &= H_i(t, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, p_1, \dots, p_{n-1}) \\ u|_{t=t_0} &= u_0^{[i]}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n-1}) \end{aligned} \right\} 1 \leq i \leq m \quad (APDES_m^C)$$

A point $X_0^{[i]} = (t_0, x_{10}^{[i]}, \dots, x_{(n-1)0}^{[i]})$ with $H_i(t_0, x_{10}^{[i]}, \dots, x_{(n-1)0}^{[i]}) = 0$ for an integer $1 \leq i \leq m$ is called an *equilibrium point* of the i th equation in $(APDES_m)$. A result on the sum-stability of $(APDES_m)$ is known in [18] and [21] following.

Theorem 4.3([18],[21]) *Let $X_0^{[i]}$ be an equilibrium point of the i th equation in $(APDES_m)$ for each integer $1 \leq i \leq m$. If*

$$\sum_{i=1}^m H_i(X) > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{\partial H_i}{\partial t} \leq 0$$

for $X \neq \sum_{i=1}^m X_0^{[i]}$, then the system $(APDES_m)$ is sum-stability, i.e., $G[t] \overset{\Sigma}{\sim} G[0]$. Furthermore, if

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{\partial H_i}{\partial t} < 0$$

for $X \neq \sum_{i=1}^m X_0^{[i]}$, then $G[t] \overset{\Sigma}{\rightarrow} G[0]$.

Particularly, if the non-solvable system is a linear homogenous differential equation systems ($LDES_m^1$), we further get a simple criterion on its zero G^L -solution, i.e., all vertices with 0 labels in [17] following.

Theorem 4.4([17]) *The zero G -solution of linear homogenous differential equation systems ($LDES_m^1$) is asymptotically sum-stable on a spanning subgraph $H \leq G[LDES_m^1]$ if and only if $\text{Re}\alpha_v < 0$ for each $\bar{\beta}_v(t)e^{\alpha_v t} \in \mathcal{B}_v$ in ($LDES^1$) hold for $\forall v \in V(H)$.*

§5. Conclusions

For human beings, the world is hybrid and filled with contradictions. That is why it is said that *all contradictions are artificial or man-made, not the nature of world* in this paper. In philosophy, a mathematics is nothing else but a set of *symbolic names with relations*. However, as *Lao Zi* said *name named is not the eternal name, the unnamable is the eternally real and naming is the origin of things* for human beings in his *TAO TEH KING*, a well-known Chinese book. It is difficult to establish such a mathematics join tightly with the world. Even so, for knowing the world, one should develops mathematics well by turning all these mathematical systems with artificial contradictions to a compatible system, i.e., out of the classical run in mathematics but return to their origins. For such an aim, geometry is more applicable, which is an encouraging thing for mathematicians in 21th century.

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